

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX METALLIC FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES. PART VI. CONDUCTOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF CADMIUM FERROCYANIDE

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Studies on the composition of cadmium ferrocyanide have been further extended. Conductometric studies support the results of the thermometric and potentiometric studies. The compound K_2CdFeC_6 is formed, but the composition is also influenced by hydrolysis and adsorption.

'Analar' (B. D. H.) reagents were used. Preparation of standard solutions (Part IV, this journal, 1948, 25, 185) and all further dilutions were made with conductivity water. The arrangement was similar to the one used previously (Part III, this journal, 1948, 25, 27) except that the induction coil was replaced by a low frequency oscillator ($\nu = 1240$). The titrations were similarly carried out in the aqueous and aqueous-alcoholic media. The conductance after each addition was also corrected (*loc. cit.*). With different concentrations of the two salt solutions, the titrations were carried by the direct and the reverse methods, *i.e.*, when cadmium sulphate from the burette was added to potassium ferrocyanide taken in the cell, and *vice versa*.

$M/5.40$ -cadmium sulphate would be referred as $A/1$ -cadmium sulphate solution, and $M/5.10$ solution of potassium ferrocyanide, as $A/1$ -potassium ferrocyanide solution.

Direct Conductometric Titrations

TABLE I

$A/10-K_4FeC_6$ soln. = 10 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 1, curve 1).

$A/1-CdSO_4$ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. $\times 10^3$	$A/1-CdSO_4$ added	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. $\times 10^3$
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	29.24 mhos	1.3 c.c.	11.3 c.c.	20.34 mhos
0.2	10.2	27.20	1.4	11.4	20.73
0.4	10.4	26.00	1.5	11.5	21.28
0.6	10.6	24.38	1.6	11.6	21.81
0.8	10.8	22.68	1.7	11.7	22.23
0.9	10.9	21.80	1.8	11.8	22.90
1.0	11.0	21.08	1.9	11.9	23.56
1.1	11.1	20.00	2.0	12.0	24.14
1.2	11.2	19.82			

TABLE II

A/10-K₄FeCy₆ soln. = 9 c.c. Alcohol = 1 c.c. (Fig. 1, curve 2).

A/1-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³ .	A/1-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³ .
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	18.18 mhos	1.0 c.c.	11.0 c.c.	13.25 mhos
0.2	10.2	17.29	1.1	11.1	13.46
0.4	10.4	16.38	1.2	11.2	13.92
0.6	10.6	15.43	1.3	11.3	14.40
0.7	10.7	14.87	1.4	11.4	14.59
0.8	10.8	14.31	1.5	11.5	15.13
0.9	10.9	13.80	1.6	11.6	15.54

TABLE III

A/10-K₄FeCy₆ = 8 c.c. Alcohol = 2 c.c. (Fig. 1, curve 3).

A/1-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³	A/1-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³ .
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	12.56 mhos	0.7 c.c.	10.9 c.c.	9.69 mhos
0.2	10.2	12.14	1.0	11.0	10.09
0.3	10.3	11.77	1.1	11.1	10.32
0.4	10.4	11.49	1.2	11.2	10.63
0.5	10.5	11.24	1.3	11.3	10.92
0.6	10.6	10.76	1.4	11.4	11.24
0.7	10.7	10.39	1.5	11.5	11.56
0.8	10.8	10.09			

TABLE IV

A/10-K₄FeCy₆ soln. = 10 c.c. Alcohol = nil. (Fig. 2, curve 4).

A/2-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³	A/2-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³ .
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	28.17 mhos	2.2 c.c.	12.2 c.c.	19.52 mhos
0.4	10.4	26.87	2.3	12.3	19.37
0.8	10.8	25.44	2.4	12.4	19.68
1.2	11.2	23.83	2.5	12.5	20.00
1.6	11.6	22.31	2.6	12.6	20.32
1.8	11.8	21.45	2.8	12.8	20.92
2.0	12.0	20.51	3.0	13.0	21.67
2.1	12.1	20.00			

TABLE V

A/10-K₄FeCy₆=9 c.c. Alcohol=1 c.c. (Fig. 2, curve 5).

A/2-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³	A/2-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³ .
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	18.87 mhos.	1.9 c.c.	11.9 c.c.	14.42 mhos.
0.4	10.4	18.24	2.0	12.0	14.20
0.8	10.8	17.42	2.1	12.1	14.40
1.0	11.0	16.92	2.2	12.2	14.70
1.2	11.2	16.58	2.4	12.4	15.22
1.4	11.4	15.84	2.6	12.6	15.65
1.6	11.6	15.37	2.8	12.8	16.10
1.8	11.8	14.84	3.0	13.0	16.67

TABLE VI

A/10-K₄FeCy₆=8 c.c. Alcohol=2 c.c. (Fig. 2, curve 6).

A/2-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³ .	A/2-CdSO ₄ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ³ .
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	13.42 mhos.	1.8 c.c.	11.8 c.c.	10.93 mhos.
0.4	10.4	13.05	1.9	11.9	11.12
0.8	10.8	12.48	2.0	12.0	11.27
1.0	11.0	12.16	2.2	12.2	11.68
1.2	11.2	11.79	2.4	12.4	12.16
1.4	11.4	11.40	2.6	12.6	12.53
1.6	11.6	10.94	2.8	12.8	12.99
1.7	11.7	10.78			

Reverse Titrations

TABLE VII

A/10-CdSO₄ soln.=10 c.c. Alcohol=1 ml. (Fig. 3, curve 7).

A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴ .	A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	90.12 mhos	1.7 c.c.	11.7 c.c.	173.2 mhos
0.2	10.2	104.0	1.8	11.8	177.4
0.4	10.4	115.5	1.9	11.9	190.4
0.6	10.6	124.0	2.0	12.0	205.1
0.8	10.8	129.4	2.2	12.2	233.0
1.0	11.0	139.3	2.3	12.3	246.0
1.2	11.2	149.3	2.4	12.4	258.0
1.4	11.4	159.6	2.5	12.5	272.8
1.6	11.6	169.4			

TABLE VIII

A/10-CdSO₄=9 c.c. Alcohol=1 c.c. (Fig. 3, curve 8).

A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴	A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴ .
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	57.14 mhos	1.4 c.c.	11.4 c.c.	120.0 mhos
0.2	10.2	67.55	1.5	11.5	124.2
0.4	10.4	76.47	1.6	11.6	127.6
0.6	10.6	82.79	1.7	11.7	136.1
0.8	10.8	91.15	1.8	11.8	146.6
1.0	11.0	100.9	1.9	11.9	157.7
1.2	11.2	110.4	2.0	12.0	168.5

TABLE IX

A/10-CdSO₄=8 c.c. Alcohol=2 c.c. (Fig. 3, curve 9).

A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴ .	A/2-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	34.48 mhos.	1.4 c.c.	11.4 c.c.	90.48 mhos
0.2	10.2	42.50	1.5	11.5	96.63
0.4	10.4	49.52	1.6	11.6	106.4
0.6	10.6	57.29	1.7	11.7	115.3.
0.8	10.8	64.5	1.8	11.8	122.2
1.0	11.0	73.82	1.9	11.9	131.0
1.2	11.2	82.96	2.0	12.0	139.6
1.3	11.3	87.60			

TABLE X

A/10-CdSO₄=10 c.c. Alcohol=0 nil. (Fig. 4, curve 10).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴ .
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	84.82 mhos	3.4 c.c.	13.4 c.c.	164.4 mhos.
0.4	10.4	97.21	3.6	13.6	168.9
0.8	10.8	108.5	3.7	13.7	174.5
1.2	11.2	117.9	3.8	13.8	179.4
1.6	11.6	123.4	3.9	13.9	186.5
2.0	12.0	132.4	4.0	14.0	193.2
2.4	12.4	141.4	4.2	14.2	205.9
2.8	12.8	150.5	4.4	14.4	218.2
3.2	13.2	159.7			

TABLE XI

A/10-CdSO₄=9 c.c. Alcohol=1 c.c. (Fig. 4, curve 11).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴ .	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴ .
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	54.35 mhos.	3.2 c.c.	13.2 c.c.	126.3 mhos
0.4	10.4	65.00	3.3	13.3	131.1
0.8	10.8	73.98	3.4	13.4	136.0
1.2	11.2	81.76	3.5	13.5	141.8
1.6	11.6	89.92	3.6	13.6	145.5
2.0	12.0	98.36	3.8	13.8	156.8
2.4	12.4	108.8	4.0	14.0	168.0
2.8	12.8	118.5			

TABLE XII

A/10-CdSO₄=8 c.c. Alcohol=2 c.c. (Fig. 4, curve 12).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴ .	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	Total vol.	Corr. conduc. × 10 ⁴ .
0.0 c.c.	10.0 c.c.	32.05 mhos.	2.8 c.c.	12.8 c.c.	90.14 mhos.
0.4	10.4	40.79	3.0	13.0	96.29
0.8	10.8	48.00	3.2	13.2	105.6
1.2	11.2	55.44	3.4	13.4	114.5
1.6	11.6	64.45	3.6	13.6	122.5
2.0	12.0	72.73	3.8	13.8	132.1
2.4	12.4	81.59	4.0	14.0	141.4
2.6	12.6	86.31			

DISCUSSION

Considering the strength of the solutions of cadmium sulphate ($M/5.40$) and potassium ferrocyanide ($M/5.10$), theoretical titre values for 10 c.c. of potassium ferrocyanide solution, for the formation of the compounds $K_2CdFeCy_6$, Cd_2FeCy_6 and $K_2Cd_2(FeCy_6)_2$ in direct titrations are respectively 10.58, 21.16, and 15.87 c.c. of cadmium sulphate solution. The theoretical titre values for 10 c.c. of cadmium sulphate solution for the formation of the above compounds in the reverse titrations would be 9.45, 4.72 and 6.3 c.c. of potassium ferrocyanide solution.

The observed titre values in aqueous medium in direct titrations are slightly higher than the theoretical titre values required for the formation of the compound $K_2CdFeCy_6$. In the reverse titrations the observed value in aqueous medium is lower than the theo-

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

retical one required for the formation of the same compound. The effect of addition of alcohol in increasing amounts in direct titrations is to gradually decrease the observed titre values; in the reverse titrations an increase is observed under the same conditions.

The discrepancy between the observed and the theoretical titre values in aqueous medium in the case of direct and reverse titrations is due to hydrolysis of the precipitated cadmium ferrocyanide (cf. Part IV, *loc. cit.*). In the presence of increasing amounts of alcohol the hydrolysis of the compound is checked to some extent, and it is observed that the titre values approach more or less the theoretical ones in the direct and the reverse cases in the presence of 20% alcohol (by volume). The adsorption of Cd⁺⁺ and (FeCy₆^{///}) ions by the precipitated compound from the surrounding solution also explains this discrepancy to some extent, but, as has been previously observed (*loc. cit.*), it appears that the role of hydrolysis in the precipitation of the compound is predominant.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

Hence the results of the thermometric, potentiometric and conductometric titrations can be correlated, and a conclusive evidence is obtained for the formation of the compound $K_2CdFeCy$.

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